

Study on the Efficiency of After- sales Support of Water Service Providers in Boracay Island, Malay, Aklan

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the efficiency of after-sales support provided by water service providers (WSPs) in Boracay Island as perceived by consumers, and examines whether the nature of the concern and consumer classification influence these perceptions. Boracay presents a unique context due to its duopolistic market structure—an uncommon characteristic in the Philippine public service sector. The study evaluates the efficiency using key performance indicators such as maximum response time, resolution rate, first response rate, customer effort, first call resolution, customer satisfaction, customer retention, and net promoter score. A quantitative, descriptive-inferential research design was employed, involving 324 customers of the Boracay Island Water Company Inc. (BIWC) and Boracay Tubi System Inc. (BTSI). Data were gathered using a validated questionnaire, with statistical analyses—including measures of association, rank-biserial correlation, and effect size—used to assess the relationships between after-sales efficiency metrics and independent variables (WSP, consumer classification, and nature of concern). Inferential methods such as Chi-Square Analysis, Wilcoxon Test, Mann-Whitney U Test, and Kruskal-Wallis Test revealed that, overall, WSPs provide efficient to highly efficient after-sales support ($p > 0.01$). However, disaggregated data showed variability in efficiency across consumer types and concern categories. Some key metrics demonstrated statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$, effect size = 0.074), although most results indicate a generally uniform perception of service efficiency across providers and classifications.

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Based on these findings, the study recommends implementing a systematized and anonymous after-sales service process which incorporates consumer classification and nature of concern, leading to the development of the NECAR model. Additionally, the creation of a user-friendly digital platform is proposed to improve consumer access to support services. The results also underscore the need for standardized national performance benchmarks for public utilities, which can guide key performance indicators in after-sales service delivery.

Keywords: *After-sales Support, Consumer Behavior, Consumer Classification, Duopoly, Water Service Provider, Utilities.*

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INTRODUCTION

One of the most vital factors for the business' success is their after-sales support, or the services and assistance a company provides to customers after they have purchased a product or service. This is to ensure customer satisfaction, build brand loyalty, and encourage repeat business, as studied by Shokouhyar, et. Al (2020), who correlates after-sales support and customer satisfaction. Using RFM clustering technique, they figured out that the respondents resonate to the SERVQUAL model by Parasuraman,et.al (1988): this model focuses on five key dimensions of service quality which are reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness. The first key dimension, reliability, focuses on giving the service in the right way. It also reflects the consistency that the services were given to its consumers. The second dimension, tangibles, refers to how the service looks, including the facility, equipment and staff. The third dimension, responsiveness, measures the readiness and preparation of the personnel in the needs and requests of its customers. The fourth dimension, assurance, measures the level of trustworthiness, credibility, and competence of service providers. Finally, empathy measures the degree of service providers to understand and respond to the need of customers.

The SERVQUAL Model was the basis for Gastezzi,et.al's (2024) study, which listed different key metrics that can be used by service providers in any industry:

- Customer Retention (CR) is defined as the number of existing customers that will still continue to avail the products/services after a period of time Usually expressed as customer retention score.
- Customer Satisfaction (CSA) - this specifically targets interactions after support has been taken. Usually, this score is determined by having a five-point scale.Usually expressed as customer satisfaction score.
- Customer Effort (CE) - measures how much work utility customers need to put in to engage with the company. This includes their navigation of different portals used, direct interactions with the agent, and resolution of issues on-call if the issue does not need site inspection and/or troubleshooting. Usually expressed as customer effort score.

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- First Call Resolution (FCR) or Ticket Reopens- is defined as the elimination of the need of the customers to follow-up on their query, allowing more time for the customer service department to answer more complex questions and deliver high value services to the customers.
- First Reply Time (FRT) or First Response Time- refers to the time it takes for the customer service to respond to a call, email, chat or inquiry. Response time will equal the total time taken over the total number of responses. In terms of parameters for first time reply, there is no established and unified value in the Philippine water service sector. However, Wren (2024) calculates a maximum of 5 hours is the accepted for response time for all the methods. This will be the parameter that will be used for the study.
- Resolution Time - refers to the duration needed by the company to resolve a problem; this only applies to service, personnel and technical concerns. Same with first reply time, Philippine water service industry has yet to establish a unified parameter for resolution time; multiple citizen's charter for water district in Aklan and in Visayas (Leyte Metro Water District, 2024; Numancia Water District, 2024; Metro Kalibo Water District, 2024; Buruanga, Aklan, 2024) however suggests a maximum of 5-day full resolution time for service-related problems. For complex concerns such as lack of water supply, temporary solutions such as alternative water supply distributions through water tankers should be strictly implemented while full resolution is taking place.
- Quantity of Resolution/Resolution Rate - shows how many issues were resolved and closed within a designated time period. This can be expressed on percentage, compared against the total concerns issued, or be compared against a maximum resolution rate;
- Net Promoter Score - shows the tendency for the existing customer to recommend the product/services to their peers.

These studies on after-sales support revolves on a competitive market where customers have a buyer power, they can seek alternatives, and switch on different companies if needed. Only few have probed to customer support where competition is high and there is a possibility that pricing is volatile—such is the case of Boracay Island, where the water utility is duopolistic and the two water service providers are governed by two different regulatory bodies.

With this gap, the study aims to determine the consumer perception on the efficiency of service providers on a duopolistic competition, and whether the nature of concern of the consumer, as well as the consumer classification, affects the perceived efficiency of the consumers. Nature of concern, categorized by four groups as suggested by Lee, et.al (2010), relies on whether they are time-based, company-based or service-based. The nature of concern might affect their perception on the efficiency, as supported by Oliver's (1980) Expectation-Confirmation Theory; consumer classification will also be tested as one of the variables, which can be attributed to Customer Expectation Management Theory and Perceived Value Theory by Zeithaml et.al (1993) and Industrial vs. Consumer Buying Behavior by Sheth (1973).

Given these related studies and theories, it is therefore imperative for all products and services to prioritize customer service support and to create a system that will satisfy the needs of their clients. With the market competition in play, behaviors changed on customer preferences especially in fields

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where competition is stiff and independent on one another. Related Philippine laws such as the Consumer Act of the Philippines of 1992 and the Public Service Act of 1936 (amended last 2022 through Republic Act 11659) also emphasize the importance of customer service, and must therefore be prioritized, public utilities included.

Research Questions

1. What are the different key metrics of after-sales support?
2. What are the categorization of the respondents based on their water service provider, consumer classification, and nature of concern ?
3. What is the efficiency of the after-sales support as perceived by the respondents, if grouped based on water service provider, consumer classification and nature of concern?
4. Is there a significance between the water service providers, consumer classification and nature of concern to the efficiency given by the respondents?
5. What recommendations can be suggested in after-sale support based on the results?

METHODS

Study Design

The study used a quasi-experimental, non-equivalent control group design with an additional factorial analysis to determine whether nature of concern and consumer classification has a significant relationship in the efficiency metrics. Respondents were divided into two equal groups, based on their water service providers. After that, a subgroup based on the nature of their concerns and consumer classification was done to each of the respondents. This yields to 16 groups of respondents, considering their water service provider, consumer classification, and nature of concern (BIWC customers, Residential, General Inquiry -BIRG, BIWC customers, Residential, Service Concern-BIRS, BIWC customers, Residential, Technical Concern -BIRT, BIWC customers, Residential, Personnel Concern-BIRP, BIWC customers, Commercial, General Inquiry -BICG, BIWC customers, Commercial, Service Concern-BICS, BIWC customers, Commercial, Technical Concern -BICT, BIWC customers, Commercial, Personnel Concern-BICP, BTSI customers, Residential, General Inquiry -BTRG, BTSI customers, Residential, Service Concern- BTRS, BTSI customers, Residential, Technical Concern – BTRT, BTSI customers, Residential, Personnel Concern- BTRP, BTSI customers, Commercial, General Inquiry - BTCG, BTSI customers, Commercial, Service Concern- BTCC, BTSI customers, Commercial, Technical Concern -BTCT, and BTSI customers, Commercial, Personnel Concern-BTCP).

Instrumentation

Research instrument used was printed questionnaires that employ guided response type of questions and is translated to three languages (English, Tagalog and Aklanon) for ease of understanding given the diversity of BIWC and BTSI customers. Pilot testing was done with 20 respondents to determine the questionnaire's validity and to check if further improvement must be done before the proper survey activity. Cronbach Alpha testing (Cronbach, 1951) yields to a value of 0.8404, an acceptable value for consistency and reliability. The questionnaire was divided into three parts:

- The first part includes open and close-ended questions that determines the respondent's name (can be a nickname), respondent's age, barangay, water service provider, nature of concern submitted, method used for submission and estimated date of concern;
- The second part includes questions answerable by "yes", "no" and "does not apply", which is tailored to determine the response rate and resolution rate of their concern and;

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- The third part include a five-point Likert scale with seven statements that will be rated by the respondents from strongly disagree to strongly-agree, involving the remaining key metrics for efficiency: customer retention, customer satisfaction, first reply time, net promoter score and customer effort in platform navigation and customer interaction.

Data Analysis

Measures of central tendency was determined to describe the central position of the data. To determine this, numerical values were assigned to the respondent's options: for yes/no questions, binary numbers were assigned (1 for yes and 0 for no). For Likert Scale, numbers 1 to 5 were assigned on each scale, with 1 being strongly disagree to 5 being strongly agree.

Aside from calculating the measures of central tendency, Chi-square for Independence will be used to test the significant association between groups with discrete data which includes the water service provider and consumer classification of the respondents. The Likert scale of the study will be analyzed using weighted mean and Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to determine the efficiency, and Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis test for testing the difference between groups. Post Hoc Test such as Dunn's test may be done if the hypothesis is proved to be significant. The effect size for Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis test was calculated and was compared with Cohen's value or Cohen's D (Cohen,1988) to determine whether there is a negligible, moderate or large difference between group. Calculated mean and percentage efficiency from the assigned numerical value of each rank will be evaluated based on the following: a) values of 1.00-1.80/0-20% shows very low efficiency; b) 1.81-2.060/21-40% shows low efficiency; c) 2.61-3.40/41-60% shows moderate efficiency; d) 3.41-4.20/61-80% shows high efficiency and; e) 4.21-5.00/81-100% shows very high efficiency.

RESULTS

The respondents were profiled based on their barangay, age, consumer classification, platform used for submission of concern, nature of concern, and estimated time the concern was submitted (expressed in month and year). Tables 1 to 6 show the profile of the respondents.

Table 1. Respondent's Profile in Terms of Barangay

Barangay	BIWC	BTSI	Total
Yapak	65 (20.06%)	26 (8.02%)	91 (28.09%)
Balabag	38 (11.73%)	54 (16.67%)	92 (28.40%)
Manocmanoc	59 (18.21%)	82 (25.31%)	141 (43.52%)

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents based on barangay. It shows that most of the respondents for the study are from Brgy. Manocmanoc with 43.52% of the total respondents. This is followed by the respondents at Brgy. Balabag at 28.4% and Brgy.Yapak at 28.09%.The distribution of respondents is being attributed to the population size of the three barangays where Brgy. Manocmanoc

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has the highest at 20,504, followed by Brgy. Balabag at 10,282 and Brgy. Yapakat 7,016 based on 2020 population census (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2021).

Table 2. Respondent's Profile in Terms of Age

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
18-23	30	9.23%
24-29	68	20.92%
30-35	59	18.15%
36-41	50	15.38%
42-47	46	14.15%
48-53	42	12.92%
54-59	19	5.85%
60-65	7	2.15%
66-71	3	0.92%

The respondents were categorized into different age groups as shown in Table 2 to assess the generational distribution of the sample. A greater number of the respondents falls within the age range of ages 24-29, accounting for 20.92% of the total respondents. This was followed by the respondents at the age of 30-35 at 18.15%. The least represented age group was at ages 66-71 at 0.92%. Measures of central tendency of the age was calculated, leading to the following results:

- Mean was calculated to be 37.48; it can be said that the average age of the respondents is 37 years old. Note that outliers might be present with the calculated mean;
- Median was calculated to be 36.1; it can be said that the equal values of the respondents can be observed before and after the age of 36;
- Mode was calculated to be 28.35; it can be said that most of the respondents are around 28 years old

Table 3. Respondent's Profile in Terms of Consumer Classification

Consumer Classification	BIWC	BTSI	Total
Residential	93 (28.70%)	100 (30.86%)	193 (59.57%)
Commercial	69 (21.30%)	62 (19.14%)	131 (40.43%)

The researcher attained an equal number of respondents for each water service provider as shown in Table 3; however, due to varying willingness of the potential respondents to participate to the study, the distribution of the consumer classification differed on both of the water service providers. It can be seen that most of the respondents are from residential classification, due to stricter nature of commercial establishments which requires further approval before participating on the survey. A total of 59.57% were residential consumers, whereas 40.43% were commercial consumers. BIWC cover 28.70% of the respondents that have residential accounts and 21.30% that have commercial accounts; 30.86% of the total respondents were BTSI residential consumers, and 19.14% of them were BTSI commercial consumers.

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Table 4. Respondent's Profile in Terms of Platform Used

Platform Used	BIWC	BTSI	Total
Traditional	116 (35.80%)	96 (29.63%)	212 (65.43%)
Digital	46 (14.20%)	66 (20.37%)	112 (34.57%)

Table 4 reflects that 65.43% of the respondents used the traditional platform which includes walk-in and direct call to hotline numbers, whereas 34.57% of them used digital platforms through messaging in social platforms, e-mail and SMS messages.

Table 5. Respondent's Profile in Terms of Nature of Concern

Nature of Concern	BIWC	BTSI	Total
General Inquiry	51 (15.74%)	40 (12.35%)	91 (28.09%)
Service Concern	98 (30.25%)	117 (36.11%)	215 (66.36%)
Technical Concern	10 (3.09%)	5 (1.54%)	15 (4.63%)
Personnel Concern	3 (0.93%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.93%)

Based on the nature of concern, service concern has the highest percentage at 66.36%, followed by general inquiry at 28.09% as shown in Table 5. Technical concern and personnel concern has the least number at 4.63% and 0.93%, respectively. Most of the complaints regarding service includes: low water and changes in pressure, whereas general inquiry was mostly about the rates of the WSPs.

Table 6. Respondent's Profile in Terms of Estimated Date the Concern was Submitted

Month Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
Jan-2020 to Jul-2020	1	0.31%
Aug-2020 to Feb-2021	2	0.62%
Mar-2021 to Sep-2021	9	2.77%
Oct-2021 to Apr-2022	5	1.54%
May-2022 to Nov-2022	1	0.31%
Dec-2022 to Jun-2023	33	10.15%
Jul-2023 to Jan-2024	29	8.92%
Feb-2024 to Aug-2024	151	46.46%
Sep-2024 to Mar-2025	93	28.62%

The profile for the estimated date of submission of concern shown at Table 6 indicates that most of the sample data submitted their concerns around February 2024 to August 2024. Calculating the mean, median and mode of the dates shows that:

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- The average month for the date of submission of the respondent's concern is around March 2022 based on calculated mean;
- Equal submission of concerns can be observed before and after August 2024;
- With the mode value of June 2024, it can be said that most of the concerns were submitted by the respondents around the said month.

Table 7. Perceived Efficiency by the Respondents, Grouped Based on Water Service Provider

Key Metric	WSP A			WSP B		
	% Response	p-value	Interpretation	% Response	p-value	Interpretation
Maximum Response Rate	98.77%	<0.01	Highly efficient	96.91%	<0.01	Highly efficient
Maximum Resolution Rate	95.54%	<0.01	Highly efficient	94.21%	<0.01	Highly efficient

*less than 5 hours for maximum response rate and less than 5 days for maximum resolution rate

Key Metric	WSP A			WSP B		
	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation
Customer Effort, Navigation of Platforms	4.45	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.33	<0.01	Highly efficient
First Response, Perceived Efficiency	4.33	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.31	<0.01	Highly efficient
Customer Effort, Interaction	4.39	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.33	<0.01	Highly efficient
First Call Resolution	4.35	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.31	<0.01	Highly efficient
Customer Satisfaction	4.44	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.36	<0.01	Highly efficient
Customer Retention	4.44	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.39	<0.01	Highly efficient
Net Promoter Score	4.51	<0.01	Highly efficient	4.41	<0.01	Highly efficient

Given the possible comparative implication of the analysis, there is a potential risk of reader bias influencing the interpretation of results. To mitigate this, the identities of the two companies have been anonymized in the efficiency section (WSP A and WSP B). These aliases are used exclusively for the evaluation and do not reflect the actual company names.

Table 7 shows the calculated mean score of the respondents based on each key metrics. It can be seen that most of the consumers found the after-sales support of their water service providers highly efficient, with the highest value of 4.51 (net promoter score). P-values using Chi-Square for Goodness of Fit, as compared to the industry standard of 75% first call resolution (US GPO,2000) and Wilcoxon Signed Ranked test shows that the perceived efficiency of the respondents are significantly different than that of neutral, with values $p < 0.01$.

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Table 8. Perceived Efficiency by the Respondents, Grouped Based on Consumer Classification

Key Metric	Residential			Commercial		
	% Response	p-value	Interpretation	% Response	p-value	Interpretation
Maximum Response Rate	97.38%	<0.01	Highly Efficient	97.38%	<0.01	Highly Efficient
Maximum Resolution Rate	93.88%	<0.01	Highly Efficient	96.51%	<0.01	Highly Efficient

*less than 5 hours for maximum response rate and less than 5 days for maximum resolution rate

Key Metric	Residential			Commercial		
	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation
Customer Effort, Navigation of Platforms	4.09	<0.01	Efficient	4.03	<0.01	Efficient
First Response, Perceived Efficiency	3.99	<0.01	Efficient	3.94	<0.01	Efficient
Customer Effort, Interaction	4.04	<0.01	Efficient	3.98	<0.01	Efficient
First Call Resolution	4.02	<0.01	Efficient	3.98	<0.01	Efficient
Customer Satisfaction	4.05	<0.01	Efficient	4.05	<0.01	Efficient
Customer Retention	4.09	<0.01	Efficient	4.03	<0.01	Efficient
Net Promoter Score	4.10	<0.01	Efficient	4.11	<0.01	Efficient

Table 8 shows that the perceived efficiency after the data was grouped based on consumer classification. It generally reflects a mean score of “efficient” all throughout the key metrics. While the aggregated data grouped by Water Service Providers (WSPs) indicated a high level of efficiency overall, disaggregating the same data based on consumer classification revealed “efficient” results. This discrepancy suggests that performance may not be uniform across consumer types, and that certain classifications—potentially residential or commercial—may be receiving services at a varying level. These findings highlight the importance of analyzing performance at multiple levels to show and solve internal inefficiencies.

Table 9. Perceived Efficiency by the Respondents, Grouped Based on Nature of Concern

Key Metric	General Inquiry			Service Concern		
	% Response	p-value	Interpretation	% Response	p-value	Interpretation
Maximum Response Rate	96.70%	<0.01	Highly Efficient	99.07%	<0.01	Highly Efficient
Maximum Resolution Rate	N/A	N/A	N/A	94.42%	<0.01	Highly Efficient

*less than 5 hours for maximum response rate and less than 5 days for maximum resolution rate

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Key Metric	General Inquiry			Service Concern		
	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation
Customer Effort, Navigation of Platforms	4.03	<0.01	Efficient	4.07	<0.01	Efficient
First Response, Perceived Efficiency	4.00	<0.01	Efficient	3.99	<0.01	Efficient
Customer Effort, Interaction	3.99	<0.01	Efficient	4.05	<0.01	Efficient
First Call Resolution	4.03	<0.01	Efficient	3.98	<0.01	Efficient
Customer Satisfaction	4.07	<0.01	Efficient	4.05	<0.01	Efficient
Customer Retention	4.04	<0.01	Efficient	4.08	<0.01	Efficient
Net Promoter Score	4.10	<0.01	Efficient	4.11	<0.01	Efficient

Key Metric	Technical Concern			Personnel Concern	
	% Response	p-value	Interpretation	% Response	Interpretation
Maximum Response Rate	100%	0.02	Highly Efficient	33.33%	Low Efficiency
Maximum Resolution Rate	100%	0.02	Highly Efficient	100%	Highly Efficient

*less than 5 hours for maximum response rate and less than 5 days for maximum resolution rate. Personnel concern analyzed using mean score only due to small sample size (n=3).

Key Metric	Technical Concern			Personnel Concern	
	Mean Score	p-value	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation
Customer Effort, Navigation of Platforms	4.20	<0.01	Efficient	4.00	Efficient
First Response, Perceived Efficiency	4.27	<0.01	Highly Efficient	4.00	Efficient
Customer Effort, Interaction	4.33	<0.01	Highly Efficient	4.00	Efficient
First Call Resolution	4.53	<0.01	Highly Efficient	4.00	Efficient
Customer Satisfaction	4.60	<0.01	Highly Efficient	4.00	Efficient
Customer Retention	4.20	<0.01	Efficient	4.33	Highly Efficient
Net Promoter Score	4.13	<0.01	Efficient	4.00	Efficient

Table 9 shows the efficiency of after-sales efficiency after the responses were grouped based on the nature of the concern. The results vary from “low efficiency” to “highly efficient”, with the highest value of 4.60 on customer satisfaction for those submitted technical concerns and lowest at personnel concern on maximum response rate. This suggests that certain types of issues—such as inquiries, service, technical or personnel—may be handled less efficiently than others. The results indicate that

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while WSPs may perform well in aggregate, performance varies depending on the specific nature of the concerns addressed.

Table 10. Association on the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent’s Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, and Nature of Concern, in terms of Maximum Response Time

Key Metric #1: Maximum Response Time				
Mean =	0=“No” for 97.84% of the respondents			
Median =	0=“No” at N ₁₆₂			
Mode =	“No” at f=317			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	
p-value	0.159	0.880	<0.01	
Interpretation	<i>No association</i>	<i>No association</i>	<i>Has an association</i>	

Table 10 shows the measures of central tendency and results of hypothesis testing for first response time. The calculated mean, median, and mode was found out to be “0”, which is interpreted as “no”. Generally, the three measures of central tendency for first response time reflects that most of the respondents on all of the sample population answered that the water service providers do not exceed the 5-hour (for general queries) and 5-day (for other concerns) maximum first response time. Using Chi-Square analysis to test whether the respondent’s WSP and consumer classification has an association with the efficiency of the after sales support in terms of maximum response time, the calculated values of $p = 0.159$ and $p = 0.880$ shows that there is no significant relationship on both variables. However, result show that there is an association between the nature of concern and the efficiency given by the respondents, with $p < 0.01$.

Table 11. Association of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent’s Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, and Nature of Concern, in terms of Acceptable Maximum Resolution Time

Key Metric #2: Acceptable Maximum Resolution Time				
Mean =	0=“No” for 94.85% of the respondents			
Median =	0=“No” at N ₂₃₃			
Mode =	“No” at f=221			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	
p-value	0.649	0.142	0.884	
Interpretation	<i>No association</i>	<i>No association</i>	<i>No association</i>	

For accepted maximum resolution time shown in Table 11, the calculated mean, median and mode is “0”, or can be interpreted as “no”. Generally, the three measures of central tendency for maximum resolution time reflects that most of the respondents who submitted service, technical and personnel concerns answered that the water service providers do not need to follow up to resolve their issues to the water service providers.

Chi square test was conducted to examine the association between the efficiency of the after-sales support in terms of accepted maximum time and the water service provider of the respondents, their consumer classification, and the nature of their concern. The results show no association, with p value

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of $p=0.649$, $p=0.152$ and $p=0.884$, respectively. It can be noted, however, that this is based on maximum resolution time due to varying parameters imposed by public sector industries.

Table 12. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent's Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of Customer Effort in Navigation of Platforms

Key Metric #3: Customer Effort in Navigation of Platforms				
Median =	4="Agree" at N_{162}			
Mode =	4="Agree" at $f=246$			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	Grouped (All Factors)
p-value	0.171	0.294	0.447	0.514
Interpretation	No significance	No significance	No significance	No significance
Effect size	-0.003	-0.068	-0.013	-0.045
Interpretation	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference

Table 12 shows the measures of central tendency and results of hypothesis testing for customer effort in terms of platform navigation. Most of the responses leaned towards "agree", with median of 4; most of the respondents also answered with "agree" as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. With these values, it can be said that most of the respondents agree that the WSP channels (e-mail, service desk, messenger, hotline etc.) are easy to navigate and use.

Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification. The results showed that there is no significance, with $p=0.171$ ($U=12,116$, $r=-0.003$) for water service provider and $p=0.294$ ($U=11,992.5$, $r=-0.068$) for consumer classification.

For the significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of customer effort (platform navigation) to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors, Kruskal Wallis test was conducted. The results showed that there is no significance between the variables, with $p=0.447$ ($r=-0.013$) for nature of concern, and $p=0.514$ (effect size = -0.045) for group of the respondents considering all factors.

Table 13. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent's Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of First Response Rate Efficiency

Key Metric #4: First Response Rate (Efficiency)				
Median =	4="Agree" at N_{162}			
Mode =	4="Agree" at $f=225$			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	Grouped (All Factors)
p-value	0.803	0.223	0.827	0.640

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Interpretation	No significance	No significance	No significance	No significance
Effect size	-0.02	-0.08	-0.007	-0.02
Interpretation	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference

In terms of the perceived efficiency of the respondents to the WSP's first response as shown in Table 10, it can be seen that most of the responses leaned towards "agree", with median of 4 and most of the respondents answered with "agree" as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. Based on these measures, it can be said that most of the respondents agree that the WSP's customer support representative is quick to reply to their concerns.

Conducting Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification showed that there is no significance, with $p= 0.803$ ($U=$, $r=-0.02$) for water service provider and $p= 0.223$ ($U = r=-0.08$) for consumer classification.

Significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of first response to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors was tested using Kruskal-Wallis Test. The results showed that there is no significance between the variables, with $p=0.827$ ($r= -0.007$) for nature of concern, and $p=0.640$ (effect size = -0.002) for group of the respondents considering all factors.

Table 14. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent's Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of Customer Effort in Interaction (Direct or Indirect)

Key Metric #5: Customer Effort in Interaction				
Median =	4="Agree" at N_{162}			
Mode =	4="Agree" at $f=240$			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	Grouped (All Factors)
p-value	0.395	0.077	0.484	0.567
Interpretation	No significance	No significance	No significance	No significance
Effect size	-0.011	-0.076	-0.008	-0.011
Interpretation	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference

Table 14 shows the measures of central tendency and hypothesis testing results for customer effort in terms of interaction. Most of the responses leaned towards "agree", with median of 4; most of the respondents also answered with "agree" as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. With these values, it can be said that most of the respondents agree that they are happy with their interaction with the WSP's customer support personnel during the submission of their query/complaint/concern.

Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification. The results showed that there is no significance, with $p= 0.395$ ($U=12,402$, $r=-0.011$) for water service provider and $p= 0.077$ ($U = 11,573.5$, $r=-0.008$) for consumer classification.

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For the significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of customer effort (interaction) to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors, Kruskal Wallis test was conducted. The results showed that there is no significance between the variables, with $p=0.484$ ($r=-0.008$) for nature of concern, and $p=0.567$ (effect size = -0.011) for group of the respondents considering all factors.

Table 15. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent’s Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of First Call Resolution

Key Metric #6: First Call Resolution				
Median =	4=“Agree” at N_{162}			
Mode =	4=“Agree” at $f=231$			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	Grouped (All Factors)
p-value	0.576	0.226	0.235	0.014
Interpretation	No significance	No significance	No significance	Has a significance
Effect size	-0.314	-0.067	-0.002	0.063
Interpretation	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Moderate difference

In terms of first call resolution as shown at Table 12, it can be seen that most of the responses leaned towards “agree”, with median of 4 and most of the respondents answered with “agree” as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. Based on these measures, it can be said that most of the respondents agree that they do not have to follow-up/ resubmit the same query/complaint/concern to their respective WSPs.

Conducting Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification showed that there is no significance, with $p= 0.576$ ($U=12,646$, $r=-0.314$) for water service provider and $p= 0.226$ ($U =11,701$ $r=-0.067$) for consumer classification.

Significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of first response to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors was tested using Kruskal-Wallis Test. The results showed that there is no significance between the efficiency of after-sales and nature of concern, with $p=0.235$ ($r= -0.002$) However, there is a significant difference in the dependent variable between the different groups, $\chi^2(12) = 25.28$, $p = 0.014$, with a mean rank score of 198.56 for (BIRG), 173.34 for (BIRS), 213.56 for (BIRT), 161 for (BIRP), 150.08 for (BICG), 131.58 for (BICS), 230.75 for (BICT), 154.22 for (BTRG), 155.94 for (BTRS), 230.75 for (BTRT), 154.32 for (BTCG), 171.99 for (BTCS), 115.17 for (BTCT). The Post-Hoc Dunn’s test using a Bonferroni corrected alpha of 0.00064 indicated that the mean rank of the following pair is significantly different: x_1-x_6 . Comparing the effect size to Cohen’s value shows that there is a moderate difference between the group, with $r = 0.063$.

Table 16. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent’s Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of Customer Satisfaction

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Key Metric #7: Customer Satisfaction					
Median =	4="Agree" at N ₁₆₂				
Mode =	4="Agree" at f=237				
Value	Water Provider	Service	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	Grouped (All Factors)
p-value	0.271		0.459	0.211	0.001
Interpretation	No significance		No significance	No significance	Has a significance
Effect size	-0.061		-0.041	-0.002	0.06
Interpretation	Negligible difference		Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Moderate difference

Table 16 shows the measures of central tendency and hypothesis testing result for customer satisfaction. Most of the responses leaned towards "agree", with median of 4; most of the respondents also answered with "agree" as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. With these values, it can be said that most of the respondents agree on the statement that they are satisfied with how BIWC/BTSI resolved their issue/concern/queries after they contacted them.

Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification. The results showed that there is no significance, with $p = 0.171$ ($U = 12,197$, $r = -0.061$) for water service provider and $p = 0.294$ ($U = 12,087$, $r = -0.041$) for consumer classification.

For the significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of customer satisfaction to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors, Kruskal Wallis test was conducted. The results showed that there is no significance between the efficiency of after-sales in terms of customer satisfaction and nature of concern, with $p = 0.211$ ($r = -0.002$) for nature of concern. However, is a significant difference in the dependent variable between the different groups, $\chi^2(12) = 32.58$, $p = .001$, with a mean rank score of 183.94 for (BIRG), 171.92 for (BIRS), 223 for (BIRT), 149.5 for (BIRP), 161.8 for (BICG), 140.61 for (BICS), 296.5 for (BICT), 150.18 for (BTRG), 149.17 for (BTRS), 296.5 for (BTRT), 144.18 for (BTCG), 176.92 for (BTCS), 149.5 for (BTCT). Comparing the effect size to Cohen's value shows that there is a moderate difference between the group, with $r = 0.06$.

Table 17. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent's Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of Customer Retention

Key Metric #8: Customer Retention					
Median =	4="Agree" at N ₁₆₂				
Mode =	4="Agree" at f=240				
Value	Water Provider	Service	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	Grouped (All Factors)
p-value	0.472		0.144	0.005	<0.01
Interpretation	No significance		No significance	Has a significance	Has a significance
Effect size	-0.04		-0.081	0.024	0.074
Interpretation	Negligible difference		Negligible difference	Moderate difference	Moderate difference

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In terms of customer retention (Table 17), it can be seen that most of the responses leaned towards “agree”, with median of 4 and most of the respondents answered with “agree” as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. Based on these measures, it can be said that most of the respondents agree that the after-sales support that their experienced positively affects their loyalty to their respective WSPs. Conducting Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification showed that there is no significance, with $p= 0.472$ ($U=12,511.5$, $r=-0.04$) for water service provider and $p= 0.144$ ($U =11,486.5$ $r=-0.081$) for consumer classification.

Significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of first response to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors was tested using Kruskal-Wallis Test. Both of the test showed significant difference in the dependent variable between the nature of concern and the different groups, with p-values, mean rank score, and effect size shown below:

- For nature of concern - $\chi^2(3) = 12.81$, $p = .005$, with a mean rank score of 157.04 for General Inquiry, 160.54 for Service Concerns, 226.7 for Technical Concerns, 147.5 for Personnel Concern. The Post-Hoc Dunn's test using a Bonferroni corrected alpha of 0.0083 indicated that the mean ranks of the following pairs are significantly different: x_1-x_3 x_2-x_3 . Comparing the effect size to Cohen's value shows that there is a moderate difference between the group, with $r = 0.024$.

- For groups, considering all factors - $\chi^2(12) = 36.93$, $p < .001$, with a mean rank score of 182.44 for (BIRG), 175.4 for (BIRS), 221.75 for (BIRT), 147.5 for (BIRP), 160.62 for (BICG), 132.04 for (BICS), 296 for (BICT), 141.63 for (BTRG), 158.21 for (BTRS), 296 for (BTRT), 134.97 for (BTCG), 174.55 for (BTCS), 147.5 for (BTCT). Comparing the effect size to Cohen's value shows that there is a moderate difference between the group, with $r = 0.074$.

Table 18. Difference of the Efficiency of After-Sales Support, Considering the Respondent's Water Service Provider, Consumer, Classification, Nature of Concern, and Group, in terms of Net Promoter Score

Key Metric #9: Net Promoter Score				
Median =	4="Agree" at N_{162}			
Mode =	4="Agree" at $f=241$			
Value	Water Service Provider	Consumer Classification	Nature of Concern	
p-value	0.177	0.667	<0.01	
Interpretation	No significance	No significance	Has a significance	
Effect size	-0.075	-0.024	0.038	
Interpretation	Negligible difference	Negligible difference	Moderate difference	

For net promoter score as shown in Table 18, most of the responses leaned towards “agree”, with median of 4; most of the respondents also answered with “agree” as level of efficiency with a mode of 4. With these values, it can be said that most of the respondents agree to the statement that they will recommend their respective WSPs to their families and friends.

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Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine the significance of the efficiency of the after-sales support to the water service provider and consumer classification. The results showed that there is no significance, with $p = 0.177$ ($U = 11,987$; $r = -0.075$) for water service provider and $p = 0.667$ ($U = 12,342$; $r = 0.024$) for consumer classification.

Significance between the efficiency of after-sales support in terms of first response to the nature of concern and group of the respondents considering all factors was tested using Kruskal-Wallis Test. Both of the test showed significant difference in the dependent variable between the nature of concern and the different groups, with p-values, mean rank score, and effect size shown below:

•For nature of concern - $\chi^2(3) = 15.19$, $p = .002$, with a mean rank score of 158.8 for General Inquiry, 159.5 for Service Concerns, 232.2 for Technical Concerns, 141 for Personnel Concern. The Post-Hoc Dunn's test using a Bonferroni corrected alpha of 0.0083 indicated that the mean ranks of the following pairs are significantly different: $x_1 - x_3$ $x_2 - x_3$. Comparing the effect size to Cohen's value shows that there is a moderate difference between the group, with $r = 0.038$.

•For groups, considering all factors, $\chi^2(12) = 30.78$, $p = .002$, with a mean rank score of 170.69 for (BIRG), 177.46 for (BIRS), 217 for (BIRT), 141 for (BIRP), 172.28 for (BICG), 143.62 for (BICS), 293 for (BICT), 142.1 for (BTRG), 150.21 for (BTRS), 293 for (BTRT), 143.2 for (BTCG), 169.41 for (BTCS), 191.67 for (BTCT).

Significant results in response time support Oliver's (1980) Expectation-Confirmation Theory, which suggests that customer perception is shaped by how well their expectations are met or exceeded. Customers anticipate different response speeds depending on the urgency and nature of their concerns. This relationship is also evident in customer retention and net promoter scores.

Given these findings, it can be concluded that consumers have expectations regarding a provider's response time, which in turn influences their likelihood of remaining with the provider and recommending the water service.

Furthermore, some significant relationships only become apparent when all factors are considered. This holistic perspective aligns with the reliability factor of Parasuraman et al.'s (1988) SERVQUAL model, as well as Zeithaml et al (1993) and Sheth's (1973) model.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The 324 respondents expect response times to vary based on the nature of their concerns, which influences their retention and likelihood of recommending the water service provider.
2. The analysis reveals that while WSPs demonstrate high overall efficiency when assessed at the provider level, a more nuanced picture emerges when the data is disaggregated. Efficiency scores decline slightly when grouped by consumer classification and nature of concern, suggesting variability in service quality across different customer segments and issue types. These findings highlight the importance of multi-dimensional evaluation to have a targeted service improvements.
3. Respondents perceive no significant difference in after-sales service efficiency between WSPs across consumer classifications when considered independently. However, notable differences

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emerge when factoring in the service provider, consumer classification, and nature of concern, particularly in retention and provider recommendations.

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